

Attitude & Perception of UG Medical Students towards Attendance

Vyankatesh Solanke¹, Pratik Sinha², Neha Patil³

^{1,2}Intern, ³student,

MGM medical college, Aurangabad(MH)

Siddhant Mathur, Prince,
Resident,

Department of Psychiatry,
MGM medical college, Aurangabad(MH)

Rajesh Kadam

Associate Professor,
Department of Pharmacology,
MGM medical college, Aurangabad(MH)

Abstract:-

Introduction: It is believe that compulsion of attendance in colleges has direct impact on overall performance of students. A cross sectional study of the perception of students towards the mandatory attendance criteria for undergraduate MBBS students.

Material & methodology: present study was conducted among the 247 students from second, third minor and major years from MGM Medical College and Hospital, Aurangabad were selected using the universal sampling protocol. Students from first year, and participants who did not consent to sharing their data were excluded. The data was collected in the period of 2 months.

Results: in the present study we found that around 65% of students believe that compulsion of attendance do not have major impact on their overall performance. 52.2% students stated that the attendance criteria for the clinical postings should be mandatory. On the other hand 68% students stated attendance criteria should not be there for theory lectures. There are some reason for absenteeism in the class like for the preparation for the exam, for the attending coaching for the entrance tests etc. Most of the students believe that the compulsion of attendance hamper their exam performance, they should get less time for daily activities etc.

Conclusion: From the present study we come to know about some conclusion like it should not be mandatory for attending classes and clinics before prelims/ final exams. Students should have some liberty to decide their curricular activities and arrange lectures according to their need. Institutions should arrange more guest lectures to provide students with some external exposure. College timings should be reduced to prevent overexertion of students. There should be some extracurricular activities should be taken for the refreshment of the students

Keywords:- Attendance, Absenteeism, UG Medical Students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is not only the delivery of knowledge, skills & information from teachers to students; it provides an individual the opportunities to analyze and act efficiently towards achieving goals and aspirations set by themselves.

Indian education policies have been designed around the idea that mandatory attendance for eligibility for exams is necessary to ensure uniform academic performance amongst various students in a class. These policies are backed by evidence suggesting that mandatory attendance is a strong motivator for attending lectures, which in turn enhances collective academic performance.⁽¹⁾

Class attendance still remains a key determinant of academic performance. Research on class attendance has shown that students with higher attendance perform better academically in both examinations and other coursework as compared to students with poor attendance⁽²⁾. Many of the studies suggests that the attendance in the class room has major impact on the development of the students career.^(3,4) There are very few studies in India on how students view mandatory attendance in medical colleges.

Many of the studies conducted all over world suggest that the performance of the students attending college regularly is better than the students which does not attend the college regularly. In some studies reasons for the absenteeism in the schools or colleges were discussed^(5,6,7)

In this study, we qualitatively evaluate the opinion of UG students regarding the mandatory attendance criteria (for theory lectures and practical lectures/clinical postings each). We aim to understand what modifications should be made to benefit students, teachers and the entire academic curriculum.

We discuss the various dimensions of students' views on attending lectures and clinical postings.

A. AIM:

To study the attitude & perception of UG medical students towards attendance.

B. OBJECTIVES:

- To study the students attitude towards compulsion of attendance in theory lectures and practical lectures/clinical postings.

- To find the reasons for absentees in academics.
- To figure out the effects of compulsion of attendance on students.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

A. Study area

The present study was conducted at MGM Medical College, Aurangabad.

B. Study period

The study period is of the this study is 2 months

C. Study design

It is a cross-sectional observational study.

D. Study population

Undergraduates from the following years who have clinical postings as well as theory lectures:

- Second year
- Third minor year
- Third major year

E. Sample size

Sample size for this study is 247.

F. Sampling technique

Sampling done by using of Universal Sampling method.

G. Inclusion criteria

Students of 2nd year, 3rd minor, and 3rd major who were interested and consented to their data being collected.

H. Exclusion criteria

1st year students, along with students from other years who were not willing to participate in the study.

A. GENDER & YEAR WISE DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY POPULATION

CRITERIA		Number	%
Gender	Male	111	44.9%
	Female	136	55.1%
Year of MBBS	2 nd Year	68	27.5%
	3 rd Minor	132	53.4%
	3 rd Major	47	19.0%

Table 1

Around 52.2% students states that the attendance criteria for the clinical postings should be there because clinical exposure is important in the medical field. Around 68% students are think that the attendance criteria for the theory lectures should not be mandatory there should be some cessation of attendance criteria.

Nearly 52.4% that is nearly more than half of students thinks that there are some marks should be awarded for the attendance in the internal assessment. Around 53.8% students stated that their parents never compel them to

I. Study Tools:

- Presented semi structured questionnaire
- Informed consent

J. Statistical analysis:

The collected data was compiled in EXCEL sheets and a master sheet was prepared. For analysis of this data the SPSS (Statistical Software for social Sciences) software version 20.0th was used. Qualitative data is represented in the form of values & percentages. The qualitative data is also presented by visual impression through the use of bar diagrams, pie diagrams etc.

Quantitative data is represented in the form of mean, SD etc. with presentation by visual impression through bar diagrams etc. For checking association between two attributes, chi-square test is applied. For quantitative data Z-test is used. Unpaired T-test is used to compare between the two groups.

K. Methods:

The present study of 247 UG medical students willing to participate were enrolled, and those not willing to participate were excluded from the study. The participants had the liberty to withdraw anytime during the study period. Primary data was collected using a preset questionnaire.

III. RESULTS

In the present study there are 111 male & 136 female UG medical students are get involved. Students from third minor get participated the most(53.4%)with great enthusiasm.

attend the lectures & practical. 62.8% of students stated that biometric attendance system should not helps in increase the attendance in practical as well as theory lectures.

43.3% students stated that they do not inform their parents whenever they skip the theory lectures as well as practical. 66.8% students stated that all departments from their college strictly follow the mandatory attendance criteria. Around 65% students from the participants think that good attendance is not directly related to academic success

Around 32% participants think that there should be attendance at one time in a day 25% participants stated that there should be the compulsion of attendance in every lecture. Around 18% of participants stated that they think attendance should be taken in any random lecture. Remaining students think that attendance should be at entry and exit time of college,

Around 42.5% students think that the biometric attendance report should be given to them only. 31% students think that attendance should be informed to both i.e parents as well as students.

Q. Biometric attendance report should be given to:

- A- Only Students
- B- Only Parents
- C- Both Students & Parents
- D- Displayed On Notice Board

Graph 1

38% students think that the attendance should be informed them every month, nearly 25% students think that attendance should be informed them on daily basis

Q. BIOMETRIC ATTENDANCE REPORT SHOULD BE GIVEN IN TIME BOUND OF: -

- A- Daily
- B- Weekly
- C- Monthly
- D- Semester Wise

Graph 2

Around 42% of students think that the attendance criteria for appearing in university exam should include average of overall attendance for every subject in theory lectures as well as practical. On the other hand 15% of students stated that qualifying criteria should be subject wise including theory as well as practical.

We evaluate some reasons for absenteeism in college from students. Many of the students bunk the college for the preparation of the examination, for the attending private coaching for the entrance tests.

B. REASON FOR ABSENTEES IN COLLEGE

		Percentage
A.	Attend private coaching classes for entrance exams	59.5
B.	The teacher covers a lot of information in short period of time facilities	44.5
C.	Lack of interest in subject	27.5
D.	Availability of entertainment	32.4
E.	Poor teaching skill of teacher	45.3
F.	Lack of confidence	23.9
G.	Family sickness	27.1
H.	Preparation of examination	62.8
I.	Too much socialization	24.7
J.	Inferior complex	21.5
K.	Fear of getting punished for not paying attention in class	30.8
L.	Lack of interest but had to join the course due to family pressure	25.5

Table 2

We evaluate some of the effects which going to happen on the students life due to compulsion of the attendance in the college. Among them Most of the students stated that they get less time for the preparation of the examinations.

C. EFFECTS OF COMPULSION OF ATTENDANCE ON STUDENTS

		PERCENTAGE
A.	Less time for preparation of exams.	74.5%
B.	Less time for completion of journals and assignments.	67.6%
C.	Less time to interact with family.	61.1%
D.	Less time to interact with friends other than college friends.	51.4%
E.	Change in daily life routines.	67.6%
F.	Increase in academic performance.	31.2%
G.	Increase in interest in the subject.	30.4%

Table 3

IV. DISCUSSION

In our study we found that Around 65% students from the participants think that good attendance is not directly related to academic success, many of the students thinks that the compulsion of attendance hampers their performance in the exams.

The study conducted A meta-analysis of college students (*Credé M, Roch SG, Kieszczynka UM. "Class attendance in college: a meta-analytic review of the association of class attendance with grades and student characteristics"*) suggests that students who attended lectures more frequently obtained better grades. This meta-analysis also demonstrated that attendance was a stronger

predictor of performance than other known variables like college entry scores, study habits and aptitude for the course.

In the other study by *Friedman et al* they found that Mandatory attendance is a strong motivator for attending lectures, which in turn enhances collective academic performance. Despite compelling evidence suggesting the benefits of attending college on a regular basis, most students believe that mandatory attendance is a detriment to their pursuits due to a variety of reasons. Some of the most common reasons for college absenteeism are as follows

- Students experience fatigue due to long college hours (8 am to 5pm),
- To prepare for examinations

- To attend coaching classes
- complete college assignments and record journals
- get together with family and friends
- pursue non-academic interests.

V. CONCLUSION

From the present study we come to know about some conclusion like it should not be mandatory for attending classes and clinics before prelims/ final exams. Students should have some liberty to decide their curricular activities and arrange lectures according to their need. Institutions should arrange more guest lectures to provide students with some external exposure. College timings should be reduced to prevent overexertion of students.

There should be some extracurricular activities should be taken for the refreshment of the students.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Friedman, Paul, Fred Rodriguez, and Joe McComb. Why Students Do and Do Not Attend Classes: Myths and Realities. *College Teaching* 49:4 (Fall 2001): 124-33.
- [2.] Credé M, Roch SG, Kieszczynka UM. Class attendance in college: a meta-analytic review of the association of class attendance with grades and student characteristics. *Rev Educ Res.* 2010;80:272. doi: 10.3102/0034654310362998
- [3.] Gunn KP. A Correlation between attendance and grades in a first year psychology class. *Can Psychol.* 1993;34:202
- [4.] Park KH, Kerr PM. A determinant of academic performance: A multinomial logit approach. *J Econ Educ.* 1990;21:101–11.
- [5.] Gurbuzoek, IjlalOeak, Emine A. Baysal The Causes of absenteeism of high school students.
- [6.] Fleming N. (1995) Attendance. Why don't they attend? London: Macmillan Press. Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA); Basic Education Sector Analysis Report, 2012.
- [7.] Devadoss, Stephen & John Foltz (1996), Evaluation of factors influencing student class attendance and performance; *American journal of Agricultural Economics*, 78 (3), 499-507.
- [8.] Von Blerkon ML. Class attendance in undergraduate course. *J Psychol.* 1992;123:487–94.